

Coir Industry: Trade Reforms and The Export Performance

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: November

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2319-961X

Impact Factor: 4.005

Citation:

Raseena, K. K. "Coir Industry: Trade Reforms and The Export Performance." *Shanlax International Journal of Economics*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 36–42.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1488507>

K.K.Raseena

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics

Sree Neelakanta Government Sanskrit College, Pattambi

(Part time Research Scholar, Dr. John Mathai Centre, University of Calicut)

Abstract

Trade is an engine of growth and the trade reforms affects the volume of trade. The features of trade reforms have significant impacts on the volume of trade and thus on growth. This paper is an attempt to explore the impact of various trade reforms on the export performance of one of the major traditional industry of India, especially of Kerala, the coir industry. The present paper covers two major trade reforms that affected the coir industry namely, the Multi- Fibre Agreement (MFA) under GATT Regime and the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATC) under WTO Regime. For the purpose of analysis, the data were collected from the Annual Reports of Coir Board and the Official Websites of Coir Board, Reserve Bank of India and Ministries of External affairs and Commerce and Industry, Government of India. For analysing the trends of exports under various trade policies, two measures were used (the CAGR and periodical growth rates). Semi log regression models were used to measure the period wise growth rates. A comparative analysis of the exports of coir and coir products from India were also done with the total exports from India for having a clear picture of the impacts of various trade reforms on exports. The analysis reveals that the relaxations of trade restrictions have positive impacts on export performance of the selected industry.

Keywords: Agreement on Textiles and Clothing, Coir Industry, Export Performance, Multi Fibre Agreement, Trade Liberalisation, Trade Reforms.

Introduction

Indian economy is basically an agrarian and industrially backward one due to various reasons at the time of its independence. Despite of the various deliberate efforts to boost the industrialisation of the country, the share of this sector to the GDP doesn't show any improvements. Due to the dominance of the agricultural sector, many traditional and agro based industries were there and developed gradually. Before independence itself we have strong trade relations with other nations especially with Arabs. These relations are the driving force of these traditional and agro based industries. But British Rule changed the pattern of industries in favour of them. Anyhow, after Independence, there was purposeful interference for building a strong industrial base for the country through Five Year Plans. As a result some basic and key industries were set up and developed in India. But the role of small scale, traditional agro based industries never fades.

Trade is an engine of growth and so it also helps for the growth of industries. Trade may be domestic or international. But international trade have more influence on the industrial performance especially due to technology transfer. But the extent of trade is influenced by some other factors. Trade reforms, both domestic and international, have in-depth and long term impacts on the export performance of a nation and thus on the growth. This paper is an attempt to explore the impacts

of various trade reforms on the export performance of one major traditional industry of India, especially of Kerala, the coir industry.

Committee on Commodity Problems (FAO, UN -2011) analysed the export trends of Jute and Hard Fibres (JHFs) during 1996 to 2010. They concluded that, the implementation of the WTO Uruguay Round agreements since 1996, and the phasing out of the Multi-Fibre Agreement (MFA) in 2004 were two important milestones for international trade in JHFs. So, this MFA, its phasing out and its removal due to the introduction of ATC under WTO have greater significance in the production and exports of fibre and fibre products. So I intended to analyse the trends in the exports of Coir industry of India during those periods. This performance was compared with the total exports of India, to infer the effects of trade reforms on the export performance of the coir and coir products. The study also focuses on the special case of Kerala due to these reforms where the industry originated and has a monopoly for decades.

Data Source and Methodology

To analyse the present issue, data were collected from the various secondary sources like the annual reports of the Coir Board, Government of India and the export data published in the Coir Board Official website. The all India export figures were obtained from the Official websites of Reserve Bank of India and Ministries of External Affairs and Commerce and Industry, Government of India. The performance of coir exports were measured using two criterion, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) and the periodical growth rates. The first measures the annual growth where the later measures the growth rate during a specific period. To calculate the periodical growth rates the semi-log regression models were used since the export data follows an exponential trend. The export of coir and coir products were compared with the total export of the Indian economy for evaluating the effects of the above said reforms.

Trade Reforms

The present paper covers two major trade reforms that affected the coir and coir product's exports namely, the Multi- Fibre Agreement (MFA) under GATT Regime and the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATC) under WTO Regime. The transition from the GATT regime to WTO regime itself has another period of reforms, namely the period of phasing out of Multi Fibre Agreement. For the better understanding of the analysis, a brief description of the various trade reforms was done as a prerequisite.

Multi Fibre Agreement (MFA)

The Multi Fibre Agreement was introduced in 1974 as a short term measure intended to allow the developed countries to adjust to the imports of fibre and fibre products from the developing countries by means of quotas. This form of protection provides a limited shield to local industry against foreign competition. So this aimed to provide sufficient time for the developed nations to develop their fibre industries and thus to reduce the imports of fibre and fibre products from developing nations [Alberto Portugal-Perez and John S. Wilson (2010)]. This is applicable to all types of fibres soft and hard. Developing and exporting countries opposing it and continued to call for a liberalisation of textile and clothing trade. As a result, in 1991 that versions of what was to become known as the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATC) – negotiated as part of GATT's Uruguay Round trade negotiations – were presented. A final version of the ATC, which set out a definitive plan for the structured removal of quantitative restrictions, was finally implemented on 1 January 1995.

The Agreement to Phase out MFA Quotas

The ATC set a four-stage quota liberalisation schedule, and is outlined in Article 2 of the Agreement. Each phase foresaw the integration of a specific percentage of textile categories based on 1990 levels. The summary of the scheduled removal of MFA quotas over the decade 1995 – 2005 under WTO Agreement on Textiles is illustrated in the table number 3.1.

Table 3.1 Removal of Quota under ATC

Removal of Quota (%)	Date of implementation
16	1 st January 1995
17	1 st January 1998
18	1 st January 2002
49	1 st January 2005

Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATC)

The integration of the textile sector into the mainstream of WTO disciplines is embodied in the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATC) which was negotiated during the Uruguay Round and is being implemented in stages over a period of 10 years. The two most significant features of the ATC are: (i) the phase-out of restraints on a predetermined schedule and within a stipulated period of 10 years and (ii) an improved, multilateral policing of additional restraints and other measures during the phase-out period through the Textile Monitoring Body (TMB) envisaged in the ATC.

Results and Discussions

Under this head it is indented to analyse the impacts of various trade reforms on the export performance of Indian coir industry. Impacts were analysed on the basis of two variables.

- Volume of exports, and
- Pattern of exports.

Volume of exports

The volume of exports of coir industry under various reform period were analysed in quantity terms and in value terms. For the purpose of analysis the different reform periods are described as,

- 1974-75 to 1993-94 - MFA Period
- 1995-96 to 2003-04 - Phase out of MFA
- 2005-06 to 2017-18 – ATC Period

During these periods the Compound Annual Growth Rates of coir and coir product's exports in comparison to the total exports from India were shown in the Table No. 4.1.

Table 4.1 CAGR of exports of coir and coir products and overall Indian exports under different reform periods

Periods		CAGR [Quantity of coir and coir product's exports (%)]	CAGR [Value of coir and coir product's exports (%)]	CAGR[overall exports (%)]
MFA	1974-75 to 1994-95	0.67	11.68	17.32*
Phase out of MFA	1995-96 to 2004-05	9.8	8.63	13.34
ATC	2005-06 to 2017 -1	16.73	13.15	11.84

Source: computed by the author from the data provided by Coir Board

*CAGR from 1979-80 to 1994-95.

From the Table No.4.1, it is evident that during the periods of quantitative restrictions on fibre products (MFA) there is only a nominal rate of growth in the export of coir and coir products from India. The total quantity of exports rose from 41834 tonnes in 1974-75 to 48086 tonnes in 1994-95. Comparing to this, during

the periods of phasing out of MFA quota there was high percent annual growth in the exports of coir and coir products. During this 10 years the quantity of export increased by 74650 tonnes. Again during the period of ATC, from 2005-06 to 2017-18, the quantity of coir export had shown a drastic growth of 16.73 percent, increased from 136026.97 tonnes in 2005-06 to 1016564 tonnes in 2017-18. Value of coir exports also had shown a positive growth rates during all these reform periods and it is highest during ATC.

The CAGR of total exports of India shown a declining trend in growth rate in contradiction to the growth rates of coir and coir products when we are analysing across these reform periods. For better understanding of the growth rates during these periods, we rely on the period wise growth rates. For measuring the growth rates of exports during various trade reform periods, regression analysis was used. For fitting a regression model, first of all, the trends of the exports during various periods were analysed. From the fitted trend forms it was clear that the exports of coir and coir products' exports (quantity of exports and value of exports) and the total exports from India were follows an exponential trend. Therefore a compound growth models were fitted for calculating the growth rates as the form 4.1.

$$Y_t = Y_0(1+r)^t \dots\dots\dots(4.1)$$

Where, Y_t = quantity of coir exports or value of coir exports or total exports
 r = compound growth rate
 t = time period

For the purpose of estimation, the model (1) was transformed to a semi- log regression model as 4.2.

$$\ln Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + u_t \dots\dots\dots(4.2)$$

Where, Y_t = quantity of coir exports or value of coir exports or total exports
 t = time period
 α, β = parameters
 u_t = random error term

Run the regression, and from these regression results, we have our compound growth rates using the following equation.

$$r = AL(\beta) - 1 \dots\dots\dots(4.3)$$

By using this equation number 4.3, the compound growth rates were calculated and were shown in table number 4.2.

Table 4.2 Growth Rates under various trade reforms

Periods	Growth rate of Quantity of coir exports	Growth rate of Value of coir exports	Growth rate of total exports from India
MFA	-0.2925	1.356	1.6618*
Phase out of MFA	1.6379	1.6617	1.6885
ATC	1.7074	1.6912	1.5779

* From 1979-80 to 1994-95.

From table number 4.2, it is clear that the export of coir and coir products have a positive growth rate in the entire reform periods in terms of value of exports but in physical terms, the export shown a negative growth due to quantitative restrictions during MFA, and when these restrictions were removed there is positive growth rates during the last two reform periods (phasing out of MFA and ATC). When comparing the growth rates, we can see that the growth rates increases when trade is more liberalised.

Comparing the export of coir and coir products that of the total export from India, it was evident that the total exports grown faster than the growth of the export of coir and coir products during periods of MFA and phase out of MFA where quantitative restrictions exists in the fibre exports. But during ATC, coir and coir products exports grows faster than the total exports. In short, the restrictive trade practices affected the export performance adversely.

Pattern of Exports

From the earlier analysis, it was evident that relaxations in trade restrictions boost the performance of coir industry. More free trade brought new technologies of productions which in turns lead to increase in production and productivity with innovative products. All these resulted in a better performance of coir industry. But when we are focussing the scenario of Kerala's coir industry, we can see that it cannot reap these benefits of liberalised trade and technology transfer. This is due to the fact that since it is a traditional industry of the State, it cannot adopt the new manufacturing technology very easily due to many reasons. Therefore, the neighbouring States like Tamil Nadu and Karnataka adopted these technology advancements and started the coir industry. Therefore the new products which is technology driven came in to market and dominated in the export basket also. Therefore the share of Kerala in total coir export decreases and those of the other states increases. This can be analysed by looking in to the composition of Indian coir export during all the reform periods (Table No. 4.3).

Table No. 4.3 Top five Coir products in the total coir exports (values in brackets shows the percentage share of each products in total coir exports)

MFA period				Phase out of MFA				ATC period			
1974-75		1993-94		1995-96		2003-04		2005-06		2017-18	
Q	V	Q	V	Q	V	Q	V	Q	V	Q	V
Coir yarn (53.82)	Coir yarn (47.14)	Handloom mats (42.01)	Handloom mats (53.27)	Handloom mats (42.13)	Handloom mats (48.98)	Handloom mats (39.27)	Handloom mats (58.72)	Coir pith (39.29)	Handloom mats (52.51)	Coir pith (54)	Coir pith (40.2)
Handloom mats (27.06)	Handloom mats (36.87)	Coir yarn (35.96)	Coir yarn (20.39)	Coir yarn (30.73)	Handloom matting (22.34)	Coir pith (25.02)	Tufted mats (9.78)	Handloom mats (31.26)	Tufted mats (22.83)	Coir fibre (36.8)	Coir fibre (27.7)
Handloom matting (8.45)	Handloom matting (10.01)	Handloom matting (13.87)	Handloom matting (17.91)	Handloom matting (15.72)	Coir yarn (16.6)	Coir yarn (13.63)	Handloom matting (9.25)	Tufted mats (14.46)	Coir pith (7.62)	Tufted mats (5.3)	Tufted mats (19.6)
Coir rugs and carpets (3.46)	Coir rugs and carpets (4.76)	Coir rugs and carpets (4.31)	Coir rugs and carpets (6.49)	Coir rugs and carpets (5.83)	Coir rugs and carpets (9.03)	Tufted mats (7.63)	Coir yarn (8.5)	Coir yarn (7.04)	Coir yarn (5.94)	Handloom mats (1.8)	Handloom mats (7.4)
Curled coir (1.82)	Curled coir (0.59)	Curled coir (1.58)	Rubberised coir (0.77)	Curled coir (2.39)	Coir other sorts (0.85)	Handloom matting (5.67)	Coir pith (4.23)	Handloom matting (2.14)	Handloom matting (3.76)	Geo-textiles (0.6)	Geo-textiles (1.6)

Source: computed by the author from the data provided by Coir Board

Pattern of exports exhibits the composition of different products of the coir industry in its total exports. This was also analysed under various reform periods. The Table No. 4.2 exhibits the top five products in terms of both quantity and value of the total exports of coir products during different trade reform periods. The table of top five products of coir exports reveals the impact of different trade reforms in the composition of coir exports. During the initial periods of MFA coir yarn dominates in total exports both in quantity (53.82) and value (47.14) and next is handloom mats. This has just reversed during the last periods of MFA. Handloom mats dominates both in quantity (42.01) and value (53.27) during this period and next is the coir yarn. This is the reason for increasing the export in terms of value during this period with quantitative restrictions. That is, due to quantitative restrictions, the composition of exports changed in favour of more finished value added goods.

During the entire period of the Phase out of MFA, the handloom mats dominates in total coir exports. At its initial time handloom mats constitutes 42.13% in terms of quantity and 48.98% in terms of value. At the end periods of the phase out of MFA the handloom mats' share in total coir exports becomes 39.27 and in terms of value it was 58.72. In this period also, the value added products dominated due to some quantitative restrictions to keep our export earnings growth. But it is also noted that one of the technology driven product, coir pith, occupies in the second place in terms of quantity and fifth in terms of value which passes through only one stage of production and treated as a waste as the traditional techniques of production were used and created much environmental problems.

When we are considering the period of ATC, coir pith ranks first in terms of quantity and third in terms of value in the initial periods. But it is a remarkable change that during the last year, coir pith ranks first both in terms of quantity and value. It is also noted that coir fibre, which is the major raw material for coir products, occupies the second position both in terms value and quantity. This change in the pattern of exports is unfavourable to Kerala since its concentration is on the product sector and the raw material is directly exports. This creates raw material shortage and high price of the raw materials. This worsens the condition of Kerala's coir industry.

Conclusion

Export performance of every nation is influenced by a lot of factors both domestic and foreign factors directly or indirectly. The above discussed trade reforms related to the export of fibre and fibre products which have serious implications on its performance. From the empirical analysis of the export data of the selected industry we can conclude that the more liberalised trade policies have positive impacts in the export performance. A comparative analysis of the total exports of India supported this concluding remark. It also caused for the increased product diversification due to technology transfer. Those who can reap these benefits can gain more from the changing scenario. In this respect Kerala achieved less in which it had a monopoly earlier.

References

- Alberto Portugal-Perez and John S. Wilson (2010). *Export Performance and Trade Facilitation Reform: Hard and Soft Infrastructure*, Policy Research working paper No. 5261, World Bank.
- Annual Reports, Coir Board, Various Issues
- Annual Survey of Industries, various years, CSO, Government of India.
- Dr. Priyanka Sahni. "Trends in Indias Exports: A comparative Study of Pre and Post Reform Period", IOSR Journal of Economics and Finance, ISSN:2321-5925, vol. no. 3, Issue, 2014, pp. 08-18.
- Dr. Thomas Issac, TM., and Ajith Mathai (2017). *Kerala Coir: The Agenda for Modernisation*, National Coir Research and Management Institute, Thiruvananthapuram.
- Economic Review -various issues, Kerala State Planning Board, Thiruvananthapuram.
- Indu.K. (2015). An Inquiry in to the Changing Market Conditions for Coir Products, Proceedings of Development Seminar, IV International Kerala Studies Congress 2015.
- Jute, Kenaf, Sisal, Abacca, Coir and Allied Fibre Statistics, 2006, 2013, 2014, 2015, FAO, UN
- Kumaraswamy Pillai, M. (2015). Marketing of Traditional Coir Products- Problems and Prospects, Proceedings of Development Seminar, IV International Kerala Studies Congress 2015.
- Lenka Fojitikova. (2014). The performance and growth of the Euro zone export in the period of 1999-2012, Procedia Economics and Finance 12 (2014) , pp. 154-163 World Trade Report (2006). WTO
- Mel Annand, Donald F Buckingham. and William. A. Kerr. (2001). "Export Subsidies and the World Trade Organisation", Research Working Paper No. 1, Estey Centre for Law and Economics in International Trade.

- Prema Chandra Athukorala (2008). "Export Performance in the Reform Era: Has India Regained the Lost Ground?", Working Paper No.2008/03, Australia South Asia Research Centre.
- Rahul Dhiman. "Study of Post Reform period of Indian Exports A Review", Review of Business and Technology Research, ISSN: 1941-9414, vol. 11, no.1, 2014.
- Reshmi, Banga, & Abhijith Das. (2010). Role of Trade Policies in the Growth of Indian Manufacturing Sector, MRPA Paper No. 35198, UNCTAD, Centre for WTO Studies.
- Shameek, Mukherjee, and Shahana Mukherjee (2012). "Overview of Indias Export Performance: Trends and Drivers, Working Paper No. 363, Indian Institute of Management, Bangalore.
- Shyam, S.S., et.al., (2004), "Export Performance of Indian Fisheries in the context of Globalisation". Indian journal of Agricultural Economics, vol. 59, no. 3, 2004, July - September.
- Twaheeb Nabi. and Dr. Jasdeep Kaur Dhami. "Analysis of Indias Export Performance in Pre and Post WTO Regime", International Journal of Enhanced Research in Management and Computer Applications, ISSN: 239-7471, vol. 2, no. 4, 2013, pp 1-5.
- Umesh, K. B., et al. "Performance Analysis of Production and Trade of Silk under WTO Regime", Paper presented in International Association of Agricultural Economics Conference, Beijing, China, August 16-22, 2009.
- UN Committee on Trade and Development report (1996). Participation of developing countries in World Trade: Overview of major trends and underlying factors Volume 1, Number 1 Article Number: 1.
- Wilson, J. S., Mann, C. L., & Otsuki, T. "Trade facilitation and economic development: A new approach to quantifying the impact". The World Bank Economic Review, vol. 17, no. (3), 2003, pp. 367-389.